

" The effect of extreme time deviation on the collapsed mass Before the formation of the zero-mass point in theoretical physics"

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Abstract:

This research paper presents a new theory that provides a different explanation for the early stages of the black holes formation , and for an element whose full effect on the formation of their singularities has not yet been fully studied, which is the direct relationship between the acceleration of the contraction of the collapsing mass and the acceleration of the effect of the distortion of time passing through it, and the way that interacts with the surrounding dark matter.

This research paper suggests that black holes are not just empty holes in the universe, but rather they are factories of black energy and particles of varying charge and interaction.

This research paper sheds light on the complex mechanism linking the rapid acceleration of the universe's expansion with its creation of new cosmic clouds and eventually new galaxies...

Keywords: Singularity, dark energy, singularity of black holes.

Introduction:

The question of the formation of the event horizon when the crust or ball of matter in the center of the collapsing star reaches in its continuous mass contraction beyond the zero-mass point despite decades of study remains without an absolute answer.

Based on the theory of general relativity, the mass of the collapsing star shrinks very quickly. This leads to an increase in the accumulation of mass in the core, which leads to a significant and rapid increase in density, and this continues due to the strong influence of gravity. The higher the density, the greater the gravitational effect. In its turn increases the mass in the core, and so on.

Exactly until this moment, and let us call it: the (B) moment, and based on all previous studies and the laws of Special theory of relativity and modern physics, all these nuclear interactions of the core mass of the collapsed star are correct, but what happens after this moment? How could these previous events form a black hole?

General relativity says that when the contraction of the core reaches a point of zero mass, the contraction reaches its maximum level, and at this point we have an accumulation of indefinite mass in a certain size known as (singularity), and that the event horizon is formed after the mass in its contraction exceeds this point with its rapid shrinking.

Then, in 1939 Oppenheimer and Snyder presented a solution to Einstein's field equations based on the Schwarzschild metric (1) proving that the final collapse of a spherically symmetric star is the collapse into a black hole.

But there is an astonishing matter that has been ignored here, which is the effect of this extremely dense , and relatively small ball, extremely hot and rotating, on the fabric of the four-dimensional universe or (space-time), and what this effect does to it in return, before this mass with its interactions and the previous mathematical equations, reaches the singularity.

The effect of this ball, whose density, gravity, and contraction increases rapidly, forms a Severely pressurized curvature on the fabric of the universe, and based on general relativity, the more this ball sinks into the fabric of the four-dimensional universe the more it Stretches it, and thus the slower the effect of the fourth dimension that passes through it, which is time.

We conclude from this dynamic situation that the acceleration of the interactions that occur to this ball is directly affected by the acceleration of the effect of the slow time passing through it is resulting from the balanced increase in the deformation of the fabric of the universe around it.

Until we reach a stage of extreme pressure on dark matter and slow time, as the collapsing mass never reaches the zero-mass point.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this research are consistent with the controversy surrounding the formation of singularities in black holes, as the mathematical equations conducted by Albert Einstein indicate that the zero-mass point will eventually be reached. However, the aspect to which sufficient attention has not been devoted lies in the effect of the fourth dimension, which includes the effect of time distortion, on the collapsed mass in real time during the collapsing.

The slowness of time passing through the collapsed mass is related to the fact that its interactions have almost stopped progressing towards the point of masslessness and infinite density. In this context, the distortion of the fabric of space-time results in our falling into a very complex and interactive scenario that resembles the shape of a water vortex, where the collapsing mass is confined to the bottom, while the outer event horizon is formed above the vortex's opening. The goal of this research is to explore this additional and obscure aspect, hinting at how important it is to understand the influence of time on the dynamical evolution of black holes, and how this influence plays a role with dark matter and its interactions within the universe.

The Theory: " Black Holes world engines " .

The inevitability of the formation of a singularity for standard black holes is the subject of many debates and studies. Among them is obstruction through the effects of quantum field theory (2), or the application of many considerations in previous research under the pretext that the collapse must stop before the singularity point is formed (3 - 4 - 5). In addition, the main obstacle since Hawking discovered radiation is: The issue of the paradox of information loss (6).

Well then, returning to moment (B), Where we have this core contracting with constant acceleration and at the same time it is bending the fabric of quadrilateral space-time, creating a direct relationship between the collapsed core and the effect of its intense mass and gravity on the expansion of dark matter surrounding it.

Where in this relationship the greater the mass and density, the greater the pressure on the dark matter, and with it the greater the distortion and slower time passing through the center of this expansion.

Then the collapsed core reaches a place due to the pressure of its mass density and intense gravity on the (dark matter) fabric of the universe, in which the speed of the acceleration of its contraction is approximately equal to the slowness of time that passes through it.

The collapsed core at the bottom reaches a quasi-stable state before it reaches the zero-mass point in its contraction. As a result of the severe deformation of the dark matter now we have a shape that I will call it a vortex for ease of description.

* When the collapsing core shrinks rapidly, the momentum of its rotation around its axis also increases dramatically (7). Until its movement gradually slows down as it sinks into the deformation of the fabric of the universe and as the time passing through it gets slower and slower.

(Drawing 1)

The formation of this distortion (vortex) in the fabric of the universe occurs at a speed equal to the speed of increasing contraction of the collapsed mass.

As soon as the mass begins to sink into the fabric of the universe, an external event horizon is formed just above the center of the deformation, according to the Schwarzschild radius, and as the collapsed mass continue its Sinking the event horizon start expansion directly and symmetrically with the expands of the vortex opening.

Once the collapsed mass reaches the maximum distortion in the quadrilateral -dimensional space-time that it can form before its interactions stopped by the slowness of time passing through it (in the vortex base), an internal event horizon is formed above it (8).

At the same time, the external event horizon that lies above the vortex reaches its maximum expansion.

The enormous gravity of the black hole begins before its formation is complete. As the collapsing mass begins to distort the fabric of the quadrilateral -dimensional space-time and sink into it, its gravity sucks in a lot of the surrounding material and sinks with it .

The majority of this material comes from the collapsed star itself. This material breaks down and collects in a very narrow area above the inner event horizon with a time relatively faster

than the time inside it, with a relatively cooler temperature, and with intense pressure applied to it due to the enormous suction power inside the vortex carrying new materials attracted and pushed down.

This causes the crushed material collected above the inner event horizon to be squeezed and flung upwards out of the vortex but not necessarily out of the outer event horizon.

(Drawing 2)

In this dynamic situation, with the stability of the quantum dispersion of the collapsed mass, the nuclear reactions and the rotational movement of the mass continue, but at a very, very slow time, while retaining the thermal radiation resulting from the collapse of the mass's shell from the first radius to the final radius before the zero mass point is formed. Hawkin's radiation occurs on the internal event horizon, where the leaking particle is squeezed and thrown out of the vortex, and sometimes out of the external event horizon, with the rest of the particles resulting from the breakdown of the attracted materials.

The evaporation of the black hole occurs when the collapsing mass through its interactions reaches the zero-mass point in its very slow passage of time.

The movement of matter continues inside this ring of intense gravity pressure and varying temperature and time, and it breaks the material into the smallest particles. As soon as a material enters the gravitational field of the black hole and is attracted to the outer event horizon, several things happen at once: In the beginning the length of the objects is distorted and increases. Time gradually slows more and more, then the body disintegrates into its basic atoms while being exposed to very intense heat within the outer event horizon resulting from the collision, coalescence and breaking of the atoms of the crushed materials.

Envisioning the intricate and dynamic environment within the outer event horizon, (situated in the region between it and the vortex opening) entails a complex amalgamation of atoms that collide and coalesce, instigating nuclear reactions. The outcomes of these interactions manifest in exceedingly high temperatures. In addition to that, particles of varying charge and interaction and raw energy got ejected from the vortex bottom and thrown into this region through an opening located exactly in the middle of the vortex opening (as materials are expelled from the vortex through this central opening in the middle of its opening, as for the circumference of this opening within the vortex opening, the materials are drawn into the vortex.)

The ejected mixture reaches the boundaries of the outer event horizon, causing a percentage of particles to fail to penetrate it. Subsequently, these particles are drawn back down into the vortex.

As soon as the crushed materials cross the outer event horizon area and enter the vortex, the grinding process persists, and as the temperature decreases, time gradually decelerates further. The intense rotation and grinding of materials inside the vortex body can release free white and black quarks with other particles. These particles accumulate in a confined and narrow region situated just above the internal event horizon.

The uniform pressure exerted from all directions on this assembly of particles arises from both the descent of new material propelled downward by the immense force of gravity and the equitably distributed pressure exerted by dark matter (the fabric of the universe) squeezing and expelling these particles upward. As a consequence of these processes, a discernible tube-like structure emerges, positioned at the center of the vortex.

The quantity of particles and the intensity of their expulsion through this tube out of the vortex are directly contingent on the volume of material consumed by the black hole. In instances of substantial material intake, this engenders adequate pressure to propel these particles with sufficient force, enabling them to breach the outer event horizon and liberate themselves from the gravitational influence of the black hole.

The relationship is direct: whenever a black hole swallows spent materials, it produces new particles of varying charge and interaction, in addition to raw energy.

The particles combine as they are expelled from the vortex, and their upward speed intensifies due to the increased influence of time passing through them. In addition to their exposure to radiation and sudden intense heat and plasma when they emerge from the vortex opening while crossing the region within the outer event horizon and then penetrating and escaping from it... constitute for us raw particles swimming in cosmic space, exhibiting significant variations in both their charge and interactive capabilities.

A fraction of these particles, constituting a specific percentage, inevitably comprises weak interactive particles—characterized as dark energy.

(Drawing 3)

The gravitational fields and quantum fields in space redistribute and collect these liberated particles into fields, where these particles interact with each other through vibrations and gravity and begin to form the atomic nucleus and then the atoms of some substance, and over the course of standard time progression, these fields of matter evolve into cosmic clouds and celestial bodies.

Results:

1) Black holes are not the result of the formation of singularities, but rather evaporate the moment they reach the zero mass point.

in which the collapsed mass continues to shrink in its very slow time and then its evaporation occurs at the moment it loses its mass.

2) Black holes play a complex role and one of the most important roles in our universe, which is creating new cosmic clouds, stars, and galaxies by consuming and recycling spent materials by breaking them up into their smallest parts and re-releasing them into the universe.

3) One of the most important results of this highly complex process is the production of dark energy, through the production of huge quantities of particles with great variation in charges and interaction.

4) This theory's prediction of how black holes produce dark energy answers a very important question which is: What is the engine behind the acceleration of the expansion of the universe?

5) This theory teaches us that the lifespan of black holes is very long because their time is almost stagnant. And that the formation of celestial bodies and stars in normal time that turn into black holes takes place at an accelerating rate. Therefore, the number of black holes in the universe is steadily increasing, which is inevitable. This brings us to the final and most important result: the continued acceleration of the expansion of the universe is inevitable due to the inevitability of the formation of black holes.

Conclusion and recommendations:

At the conclusion of this research, we find that our new theory about the formation of black holes and their major role opens new horizons for a deep understanding of the physical phenomena in the universe.

I believe that the classical description of physics is ever correct, and that reaching the concept of singularity in Albert Einstein's theory of general relativity, where density becomes infinite is an indeterministic arrival, as a result of not introducing the influence of the fourth dimension (time) on the ongoing interactions.

The conclusions in this paper allow researchers to more accurately understand how the expansion of this universe accelerates over time.

This study hopes to motivate future researchers to discover more secrets about black holes. For example, there is the old question: Is there a giant black hole in the center of every galaxy? If so, then the new question raised by this study: Are these galaxies a total or partial result of the particles produced and released by the black hole?

Over time, this research will contribute to advancing knowledge and expanding the boundaries of our understanding of complex cosmic phenomena.

Ultimately, the universe remains a field of ongoing challenges and discoveries, and this research hopes to contribute its share to advancing human understanding of the infinite mystery in this wonderful context.

Attachments:

Drawing 1:

Drawing 2:

Drawing 3:

Drawing 4:

***The 4th drawing is a two-dimensional illustration of how we view a black hole, as the distortion of dark matter is invisible to an outside observer.**

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